

Estimation of HDL and Neutrophil to Lymphocyte Ratio in Relation with Child Turcotte-Pugh Staging of Chronic Liver Disease PatientsHarpreet Singh Braham¹, Hardayal Meena², Harish Chandra Barjatya³, Kuldeep⁴^{1,4}PG Resident, Department of General Medicine, Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College & Hospital, Ajmer (Raj.)²Associate Professor, Department of General Medicine, Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College & Hospital, Ajmer (Raj.)³Senior Professor and Unit Head, Department of General Medicine, Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College & Hospital, Ajmer (Raj.)

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background and Aims: Chronic liver disease (CLD) represents a significant global health burden, characterized by progressive decline in liver function affecting protein synthesis, detoxification, and bile excretion. While Child-Turcotte-Pugh (CTP) scoring remains the standard for assessing disease severity, there is growing interest in identifying additional prognostic markers. This study aimed to analyze the relationship between High-Density Lipoprotein (HDL) and Neutrophil-to-Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR) with CTP staging in CLD patients.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted on 139 CLD patients admitted to medicine and gastroenterology wards between December 2022 and November 2023. Patients were categorized according to CTP staging, and their HDL and NLR values were analyzed. Complete blood count, liver function tests, lipid profile, and other relevant investigations were performed. Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS 25.0.

Results: Of 139 patients, 74.10% were male, with the majority (38.85%) aged 41-50 years. Alcoholic liver disease was the predominant etiology (46.04%). The mean NLR was 3.34 ± 1.17 , and mean HDL was 34.89 ± 4.25 mg/dl. NLR showed a significant positive correlation with CTP staging (Class A: 2.10 ± 1.09 , Class B: 3.05 ± 1.15 , Class C: 4.17 ± 1.21 ; $p=0.002$), while HDL showed a significant negative correlation (Class A: 36.40 ± 3.90 , Class B: 34.73 ± 4.51 , Class C: 32.01 ± 4.33 ; $p=0.032$).

Conclusion: Both HDL and NLR demonstrate significant correlation with CTP staging in CLD patients, suggesting their potential utility as prognostic markers in chronic liver disease.

Keywords: Chronic liver disease, Child-Turcotte-Pugh score, High-density lipoprotein, Neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio, Liver cirrhosis, Inflammation markers.

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Introduction

Chronic liver disease (CLD) represents a significant global health challenge, characterized by a progressive decline in liver function lasting longer than six months. This decline affects the liver's vital functions, including protein synthesis, toxin detoxification, and bile excretion [1]. The global impact of CLD is substantial, with cirrhosis accounting for 2.2% of deaths worldwide in 2016, ranking as the eleventh most common cause of death [2]. In 2017, approximately 1.32 million deaths were attributed to CLD, with a gender distribution showing two-thirds male and one-third female mortality [3]. The assessment of liver disease severity remains crucial for proper patient management and prognostication. The Child-Turcotte-Pugh (CTP) scoring system, developed initially by Child and Turcotte in 1964 and modified

by Pugh in 1973, has been the cornerstone of liver disease assessment [4,5]. However, there is growing interest in identifying additional markers that could complement existing scoring systems. The neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) has emerged as a promising marker, combining two aspects of the immune response: neutrophils representing ongoing inflammation and lymphocytes representing the regulatory pathway [6]. Studies have shown NLR's utility in predicting systemic infection and various cancer outcomes [7-10]. Additionally, high-density lipoprotein (HDL) has demonstrated significance beyond its traditional role in cholesterol transport showing anti-inflammatory properties and correlation with mortality in cirrhotic patients [11-14]. Recent research has highlighted the role of HDL in inflammatory responses, par-

ticularly through its HDL3 subclass, which has demonstrated anti-inflammatory capabilities [15]. Furthermore, HDL has shown direct connections to complement pathway elements and proteins crucial for immune system and acute phase response [16]. The liver's central role in lipid metabolism suggests that severe liver dysfunction would affect lipid profiles. Studies have shown that patients with severe hepatitis and hepatic failure exhibit significantly decreased plasma cholesterol levels due to reduced lipoprotein production [17]. Additionally, the relationship between inflammation and liver disease progression makes NLR a potentially valuable marker in CLD [18,19]. This study aims to evaluate the relationship between HDL and NLR with CTP staging in chronic liver disease patients, potentially identifying additional tools for disease severity assessment and prognostication.

Methodology

This cross-sectional study was conducted at Jawaharlal Nehru Hospital, Ajmer, between December 2022 and November 2023. The study protocol adhered to ethical guidelines and received institutional review board approval. All participants provided written informed consent before enrollment.

The sample size of 139 was calculated using the formula $n = z^2 pq / d^2$, where $z = 1.96$ (95% confidence interval), and appropriate values for probability and precision were applied. Patient selection followed strict inclusion and exclusion criteria to ensure a representative study population while minimizing confounding factors.

Inclusion criteria encompassed patients with chronic viral hepatitis, alcoholic chronic liver disease, nonalcoholic fatty liver disease and other causes of CLD such as Wilson disease, hemochromatosis and alpha 1-antitrypsin deficiency. Exclusion criteria were carefully defined to eliminate potential confounding conditions, including hepatocellular carcinoma with chronic liver disease, acute liver injury from various causes, familial dyslipidemia, diabetic nephropathy, nephrotic syndrome, kidney disease,

pregnancy, and patients under 18 years of age. Each participant underwent comprehensive evaluation including detailed history taking, thorough clinical examination, and extensive laboratory investigations.

Standard investigations included complete blood count, liver function tests, renal function tests, serum electrolytes, urinalysis, electrocardiogram, fasting blood sugar, prothrombin time-INR and abdominal ultrasonography. Special investigations focused on HDL measurement (conducted after 9-12 hours of fasting) and NLR calculation (derived from the absolute neutrophil count divided by absolute lymphocyte count from CBC differential).

The CTP score was calculated using five parameters: serum bilirubin, serum albumin, prothrombin time, ascites and hepatic encephalopathy. Patients were classified into three groups: Class A (5-6 points), Class B (7-9 points), and Class C (10-15 points).

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 25.0. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. One-way ANOVA was used for comparing multiple groups, and t-test for two-group comparisons. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

The study included 139 patients with chronic liver disease. The study subjects were distributed according to gender and age. Majority of the subjects were males ($n = 103$, 74.10%) while females constituted 25.90% ($n = 36$) of the study population. Most of the study subjects were within 41-50 years of age ($n = 54$, 38.85%), followed by 45 (32.37%) who were between 51-60 years of age.

There were 32 (23.02%) subjects between 31-40 years and only 8 (5.76%) subjects were between 18-30 years of age. The residential distribution showed that majority of participants were from urban areas ($n = 78$, 56.12%) while 61 (43.88%) belonged to rural areas (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic profile among CLD Subjects

Characteristic	Number (%)
Gender	
Male	103 (74.10%)
Female	36 (25.90%)
Age Groups (years)	
18-30	8 (5.76%)
31-40	32 (23.02%)
41-50	54 (38.85%)
51-60	45 (32.37%)
Region	
Urban	78 (56.12%)
Rural	61 (43.88%)

Table 2: Etiology of CLD

Etiology	No. of Patients	Percentage
Alcoholic	64	46.04
Chronic Viral Hepatitis	29	20.86
NASH	46	33.09

Alcoholic liver disease emerged as the predominant etiology (46.04%), followed by NASH (33.09%) and chronic viral hepatitis (20.86%). This distribution reflects the significant burden of alcohol-related liver disease in the study population and the growing impact of metabolic liver disease (NASH) (Table 2). Among comorbidities, diabetes was present in 27 (19.42%) patients while hypertension was observed in 18 (12.95%) patients. Ascites was present in majority of the subjects (n=91, 65.47%).

The mean investigative profile revealed FIB level of 6.19 ± 5.11 , total bilirubin of 2.78 ± 2.03 mg/dl, and albumin of 3.41 ± 1.17 g/dl. The mean ALT and AST levels were 43.87 ± 26.80 U/ml and 69.24 ± 36.41 U/ml respectively. The mean INR was 1.42 ± 0.45 , serum creatinine was 1.05 ± 0.32 mg/dl, hemoglobin was 10.70 ± 2.83 g/dl, and platelet count was $128.29 \pm 57.96 \times 10^3$ /cmm. The mean

Neutrophil-to-Lymphocyte Ratio (NLR) was 3.34 ± 1.17 , with mean neutrophil count of 3.87 ± 1.04 and mean lymphocyte count of 1.16 ± 0.86 . The lipid profile showed mean total cholesterol of 116.51 ± 38.72 mg/dl, LDL cholesterol of 80.33 ± 11.99 mg/dl, VLDL cholesterol of 21.34 ± 3.76 mg/dl, and HDL cholesterol of 34.89 ± 4.25 mg/dl.

According to CTP classification, majority of subjects were in Class B (n=77, 55.40%), followed by Class C (n=48, 34.53%) and Class A (n=14, 10.07%). The comparison of NLR across CTP grades showed a significant progressive increase (p=0.002). NLR values progressively increased from CTP Class A (2.10 ± 1.09) to Class B (3.05 ± 1.15) and Class C (4.17 ± 1.21), indicating that higher NLR values correspond with more severe liver disease (Table 3).

Table 3: Correlation of NLR with CTP Staging

CTP Class	Mean NLR	SD	p-value
A	2.10	1.09	0.002
B	3.05	1.15	
C	4.17	1.21	

Table 4: Correlation of HDL with CTP Staging

CTP Class	Mean HDL-C (mg/dl)	SD	p-value
A	36.40	3.90	0.032
B	34.73	4.51	
C	32.01	4.33	

HDL levels showed a significant negative correlation with CTP class (p=0.032). HDL levels progressively decreased from CTP Class A (36.40 ± 3.90 mg/dl) to Class B (34.73 ± 4.51 mg/dl) and Class C (32.01 ± 4.33 mg/dl), suggesting that declining HDL levels may indicate worsening liver function (Table 4).

Discussion

This cross-sectional study provides significant insights into the relationship between HDL, NLR, and CTP staging in chronic liver disease. Our study population demonstrated a clear male predominance (74.10%), which aligns with findings from multiple previous studies including Rudrajit Paul et al. [20] (69.2%) and Bobi Singh M et al. [21] (72.7%). This gender distribution likely reflects both biological factors and higher exposure to risk factors like alcohol consumption among males. The age distribution in our study peaked in the 41-50 year group (38.85%), corresponding with the natural history of chronic liver disease progression,

similar to findings by Rehab Badawi et al. [22] who reported a mean age of 56.37 ± 11.13 years. Regarding disease etiology, alcoholic liver disease emerged as the predominant cause (46.04%) in our study population, consistent with global trends and similar to findings by Bobi Singh M et al. [21] who reported 69.7% alcoholic etiology. The significant proportion of NASH (33.09%) in our study reflects the growing impact of metabolic syndrome and changing lifestyle patterns, a trend increasingly recognized worldwide [23]. This distribution differs somewhat from Rao BH et al. [24], who found cryptogenic cirrhosis as the predominant cause (50%), highlighting potential regional variations in disease patterns. One of our key findings was the significant positive correlation between NLR and CTP staging (p=0.002). The progressive increase in NLR values across CTP classes (A: 2.10 ± 1.09 , B: 3.05 ± 1.15 , C: 4.17 ± 1.21) reflects the intensifying inflammatory state in advancing liver disease, supporting Chen SS et al. [18] observations about the role of necro-inflammation in severe cirrhosis. This

correlation aligns with Biyik M et al.[25] findings showing NLR as an independent predictor of survival in cirrhotic patients. The relationship between NLR and disease severity can be attributed to the progressive immune dysregulation and inflammatory response that characterizes advancing liver disease. The significant negative correlation between HDL levels and CTP staging ($p=0.032$) provides valuable insights into the relationship between liver function and lipid metabolism. The progressive decrease in HDL levels across CTP classes (A: 36.40 ± 3.90 , B: 34.73 ± 4.51 , C: 32.01 ± 4.33 mg/dl) reflects the liver's compromised capacity for lipoprotein synthesis, supporting Halsted CH [17] observations about altered lipid profiles in severe liver disease. This finding is particularly significant when considered alongside Habib A et al.[13] research showing HDL cholesterol as a predictor of mortality in cirrhosis patients.

Our findings regarding HDL are further supported by Trieb M et al.[26] research demonstrating HDL-related biomarkers as robust predictors of survival in chronic liver failure. The inverse relationship between HDL levels and disease severity can be explained by multiple mechanisms, including reduced hepatic synthesis, altered lipid metabolism, and the role of HDL in inflammatory responses. This is consistent with Rao BH et al.[24] findings showing HDL as a reliable marker for decompensation risk in CLD patients. The concurrent examination of both NLR and HDL in relation to CTP staging provides a more comprehensive understanding of the inflammatory and metabolic aspects of liver disease progression.

The inverse relationship of HDL and direct relationship of NLR with disease severity suggest these parameters could serve as complementary markers to existing prognostic tools. This is particularly relevant given the growing recognition of inflammation's role in liver disease progression and the need for easily accessible prognostic markers.

The strengths of our study include its comprehensive assessment of both inflammatory and metabolic markers, the inclusion of diverse etiologies of liver disease, and the standardized measurement of parameters. However, we acknowledge certain limitations, including the cross-sectional nature of the study, which prevents assessment of temporal relationships, and the single-center design, which may limit generalizability. Additionally, the lack of long-term follow-up data prevents evaluation of these markers' predictive value for clinical outcomes. These findings have important clinical implications, suggesting that routine measurement of HDL and NLR could provide additional prognostic information in CLD patients. However, larger prospective studies are needed to validate these findings and establish definitive cut-off values for clinical use.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates significant correlations between both HDL and NLR with CTP staging in chronic liver disease patients. The progressive increase in NLR and decrease in HDL levels with advancing CTP class suggests their potential utility as additional prognostic markers in CLD. The inverse relationship of HDL and direct relationship of NLR with disease severity provides complementary information about both metabolic and inflammatory aspects of liver disease progression.

These findings have several important implications for clinical practice. First, both HDL and NLR are readily available markers that could be easily incorporated into routine clinical assessment of CLD patients. Second, their significant correlation with CTP staging suggests they could serve as additional tools for monitoring disease progression and potentially predicting outcomes. Third, the combination of these markers might provide a more comprehensive assessment of liver disease severity, incorporating both inflammatory and metabolic aspects of the disease process.

Hence, HDL and NLR represent promising markers for assessing liver disease severity, potentially complementing existing scoring systems. Their routine measurement could provide valuable additional information for clinical decision-making in CLD patients, though further research is needed to establish their definitive role in clinical practice.

References

1. Sharma A, Nagalli S. Chronic Liver Disease. Updated 2023 Jul 3]. In: StatPearls Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024 Jan-. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK554597/>
2. Global Health Estimates. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2016. Available at: https://www.who.int/healthinfo/global_burden_disease/estimates/en/. Accessed June 15, 2020.
3. Sepanlou SG, Safiri S, Bisignano C, et al. The global, regional, and national burden of cirrhosis by cause in 195 countries and territories, 1990-2017: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2017. *Lancet Gastroenterol Hepatol* 2020; 5: 245-266.
4. Child CG, Turcotte JG. Surgery and portal hypertension. *Major Probl Clin Surg*. 1964; 1: 1-85.
5. Pugh RN, Murray-Lyon IM, Dawson JL, et al. Transection of the esophagus for bleeding oesophageal varices. *Br J Surg*. 1973; 60: 646-649.
6. Avanzas P, Quiles J, Lopez de Sa E, et al. Neutrophil count and infarct size in patients with acute myocardial infarction. *Int J Cardiol*. 2004; 97(1): 155-156.

7. Biyik M, Ucar R, Solak Y, et al. Blood neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio independently predicts survival in patients with liver cirrhosis. *European Journal of Gastroenterology & Hepatology*. 2013; 25(4): 435-41.
8. Liu D, Huang Y, Li L, et al. High neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratios confer poor prognoses in patients with small cell lung cancer. *BMC Cancer*. 2017; 17(1): 882.
9. Chen S, Zhang L, Yan G, et al. Neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio is a potential prognostic biomarker in patients with ovarian cancer: a meta-analysis. *BioMed Research International*. 2017; 2017: 7943467.
10. Sato Y, Gonda K, Harada M, et al. Increased neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio is a novel marker for nutrition, inflammation and chemotherapy outcome in patients with locally advanced and metastatic esophageal squamous cell carcinoma. *Biomedical Reports*. 2017; 7(1): 79-84.
11. Kosmas CE., Martinez I, Sourlas A, et al. High-density lipoprotein (HDL) functionality and its relevance to atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease. *Drugs Context*. 2018; 7: 1–9.
12. Trieb M, Horvath A, Birner-Gruenberger R, et al. Liver disease alters high-density lipoprotein composition, metabolism and function. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta*. 2016; 1861(7): 630–638.
13. Habib A, Mihas AA, Abou-Assi SG, et al. High-density lipoprotein cholesterol as an indicator of liver function and prognosis in noncholestatic cirrhotics. *Clin Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2005; 3(3): 286–291.
14. Pirillo A, Catapano AL, Norata GD. HDL in infectious diseases and sepsis. *Handb Exp Pharmacol*. 2015; 224: 483–508.
15. Camont L., Lhomme M., Rached F., et al. Small, dense high-density lipoprotein-3 particles are enriched in negatively charged phospholipids: relevance to cellular cholesterol efflux, antioxidative, antithrombotic, anti-inflammatory, and antiapoptotic functionalities. *Arteriosclerosis, Thrombosis, and Vascular Biology*. 2013; 33(12): 2715–2723.
16. Birner-Gruenberger R, Schittmayer M, Holzer M, et al. Understanding high-density lipoprotein function in disease: Recent advances in proteomics unravel the complexity of its composition and biology. *Prog Lipid Res*. 2014; 56C: 36–46.
17. Halsted CH. Nutrition and alcoholic liver disease. *Semin Liver Dis*. 2004;24(3):289–304.
18. Chen SS, Yu KK, Ling QX, et al. Factors associated with significant liver necroinflammation in chronic hepatitis B patients with cirrhosis. *Scientific Reports*. 2016; 6: 33093.
19. Zhang H, Sun Q, Mao W, et al. Neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio predicts early mortality in patients with HBV-related decompensated cirrhosis. *Gastroenterology Research and Practice*. 2016; 2016: 4394650.
20. Rudrajit Paul, Hridish N Chakravarti, Sanjay K Mandal, et al. Study of serum uric acid in chronic liver disease and its relation with other parameters. *Int Res J Pharm*. 2013; 4(7):162-165.
21. Bobi Singh M, Achouba Singh K, Ratan Kumar Singh M. Study of serum uric acid levels among patients of chronic liver disease. *J Evid Based Med Healthc*. 2019; 6(39):2629-2632.
22. Rehab Badawi, Abu Rahma MZ, Ramadan HK, et al. Lipid Profiles as Markers for the Severity of Liver Diseases in Cirrhotic Patients. *The Open Biomarkers Journal*. 2021; 11(1): 93-98.
23. Mukherjee PS, Vishnubhatla S, Amarapurkar DN, et al. Etiology and mode of presentation of chronic liver diseases in India: a multi-centric study. *PLoS One* 2017; 12: e0187033.
24. Rao BH, Nair P, Koshy AK, et al. Role of High-Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol (HDL-C) as a Clinical Predictor of Decompensation in Patients with Chronic Liver Disease (CLD). *Int J Hepatol*. 2021; 2021: 1795851.
25. Biyik M, Ucar R, Solak Y, et al. Blood neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio independently predicts survival in patients with liver cirrhosis. *Eur J Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2013; 25(4): 435-441.
26. Trieb M, Rainer F, Stadlbauer V, et al. HDL-related biomarkers are robust predictors of survival in patients with chronic liver failure. *J Hepatol*. 2020; 73(1): 113-120.